

Abstract: This paper examines the recent trends of literature and culture studies, with a special reference to glocalization. Glocalisation is a portmanteau word created out of ‘localization’ and the ‘globalization’ which signifies a hyper-culturalism that has a connotation beyond globalization or localization. It has three sections; the first section of the paper traces the genealogical development of the trends in literary study, criticism and theorization, and how the concept of glocalization associated with the literary and cultural product emerges; the second section negotiates the nuances and its location within the discipline of literature and culture studies, and attempts to find why and how glocalisation can be a popular trend in literature; while the third section explores a case study of *Xiaomi*, one of the most popular smartphone brands, and the recent controversy of the *YouTube* vs *TikTok* to trace the element of glocalisation in the Indian subcontinent.